

Prediction of Intracranial Pressure using Standard Periodic Vital Signs

An Explorative Analysis of Periodic Vital Parameters

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ABSTRACT

Currently, to measure the intracranial pressure (ICP) there are invasive probes, which need to be positioned intraoperatively during primary surgery or as an additional bed-side procedure through a standardized frontal approach targeting the lateral ventricular system or the white matter of the non-dominant or predominantly lesioned hemisphere. As this intraoperatively approach is linked with risks, the medical research aims to find potential correlators for the ICP by investigating different biomarkers. This paper proposes a machine learning approach to predict the ICP using standard periodic vital signs and identifying potential correlators by investigating the feature importance of the models instead of using basic statistics.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, intracranial pressure, medical health, neurosurgery, Machine Learning, prediction, vital signs, traumatic brain injury

1 Introduction and Background

Invasive monitoring of intracranial pressure (ICP) is part of the standard armamentarium of neurocritical care units in high-income countries.[1] Different pathologies like traumatic brain injury (TBI), intra- and extra axial bleedings or cerebral neoplasia can cause increased ICP and therefore require continuous monitoring of pressures.[2]

To date there are different invasive ICP probes on the market, for example fluid-based systems and implantable transducers.[3,4] Technically, ICP probes are positioned intraoperatively during primary surgery or as an additional bed-side procedure through a standardized frontal approach targeting the lateral ventricular system or the white matter of the non-dominant or predominantly lesioned hemisphere.

Elevated ICP leads to reduced perfusion of the cerebral parenchyma, causing secondary neuronal injury or brain herniation resulting in poor neurological outcome. [2,5,6]

2 Purpose

Multiple studies have shown that a higher intracranial pressure (ICP) correlates with a negative outcome of the traumatic brain injuries (TBI) patient (death or neurological deficit). [8,9,10] As with other organs in the human body there are several biomarkers, which can indicate an anomaly in the functionality of the organs. For example, the cardiac enzymes troponin I and troponin T are good indicators for heart attacks or myocarditis [11]. After such events those enzymes show a higher concentration in the blood and can be used as biomarkers. Currently, for brain injuries or events there are no accurate biomarkers or correlators identified in medical research and lead to invasive procedures, which are linked with further potential risks. The eICU database provides a large data source that can be used to identify potential vital signs to predict the outcome after brain injuries. Due to the complexity in neurological deficits and the brain functionality in general, it is difficult to find a few parameters with dedicated value ranges. Furthermore, with the increase of patient vital information and development of machine learning there are new opportunities to solve this problem. Therefore, the present paper proposes a machine learning approach to examine the ICP using standard periodic vital signs. After an accurate machine learning model has been developed to predict the ICP, the feature importance of the model can be evaluated in the first step, to identify features as potential vital signs. This paper addresses following research question:

Which available patient information and periodic vital signs are important features for the prediction of ICP?

3 Data Description

The eICU Collaborative Research Database is a multi-center database comprising deidentified health data associated with over 200,000 admissions to ICUs (Intensive Care Units) across the United States between 2014-2015. The data include vital signs, laboratory measurements, medications, APACHE components, care plan information, admission diagnosis, patient history, time-stamped diagnoses from a structured problem list, and similarly chosen treatments. It is important to be aware that different care units may have different interfaces in place, and that the lack of an interface will result in no data being available for a given patient, even if those measurements were made in reality. The data is

provided as a relational database, comprising multiple tables joined by keys and can be imported via .csv-files. [7]. For the prediction of ICP the relevant tables, described in subsequent chapters, have been extracted from the eICU database.

3.1 Vital Periodics

The *vitalPeriodics* table contains periodic vital signs, which has been monitored from bedside monitors. The data are generally interfaced as 1 minute averages, and archived into the *vitalPeriodic* table as 5 minute median values. The vital signs are not validated by care staff, so data quality can vary, but the use of 1 minute averages followed by 5 minute medians before archival removes many spurious readings. To show the time dependencies, the table contains the feature *observationoffset* with values representing the time intervals of the measurement. It is important to be aware of that not all patients have the same measurements available, which will lead to missing data and is required to be considered in the pre-processing part. The Figure 1 shows vital signs from one patient over time.

Figure 1: One patients vital signs

The *vitalPeriodics* table contains following 19 features:

vitalperiodicid, *patientunitstayid*, *observationoffset*, *temperature*, *sao2*, *heartrate*, *respiration*, *cvp*, *etco2*, *systemsystolic*, *systemicdiastolic*, *systemicmean*, *pasystolic*, *padiastolic*, *pamean*, *st1*, *st2*, *st3*, *icp*.

Detailed description of each feature can be found under following link: <https://eicu-crd.mit.edu/eicutables/vitalperiodic/>

3.2 Patient

The patient table contains patient demographics, admission and discharge details for hospital and ICU stays. Following 29 features are included in the table and will be pre-processed for the model development:

Patientunitstayid, *patienthealthsystemstayid*, *age*, *ethnicity*, *hospitalid*, *wardid*, *apacheadmissiondx*, *admissionheight*, *hospitaladmittime24*, *hospitaladmitoffset*, *hospitaladmitsource*, *hospitaldischargeyear*, *hospitaldischargeyear*, *hospitaldischargeoffset*, *hospitaldischargeoffset*, *hospitaldischargelocation*, *hospitaldischargelocation*, *hospitaldischargestatus*, *unitytype*, *unitadmittime24*, *unitadmitsource*, *unitvisitsource*, *unitstaytype*, *admissionweight*, *dischargeweight*, *unitdischargeyear*, *unitdischargeoffset*, *unitdischargeoffset*, *unitdischargelocation*, *unitdischargestatus*, *uniquepid*.

Detailed description of each feature can be found under following link: <https://eicu-crd.mit.edu/eicutables/patient/>

3.3 Apache Patient Results

The *apachePatientResult* provides predictions made by the APACHE score, including probability of mortality, length of stay, and ventilation days. The Acute Physiology Age Chronic Health Evaluation (APACHE) score could be a significant feature for the prediction of ICP, because it consists of a groups of equations used for predicting outcomes in critically ill patients. Furthermore, including the patient demographics could show a potential correlation with the ICP. The *apachePatientResult* table contains following 23 features:

apachepatientresultsid, *patientunitstayid*, *physicianspeciality*, *physicianinterventioncategory*, *acutephysiologyscore*, *apachescore*, *apacheversion*, *predictedmortality*, *actualmortality*, *predictediculos*, *actualiculos*, *predictedhospitalmortality*, *actualhospitalmortality*, *predictedhospitalallos*, *actualhospitalallos*, *preopmi*, *preopcardiacath*, *ptcawithin24h*, *unabridgedunitlos*, *unabridgedhospllos*, *actualventdays*, *preventdays*, *unabridgedactualventdays*.

Detailed description of each feature can be found under following link: <https://eicu-crd.mit.edu/eicutables/apachepatientresult/>

4 Data Preprocessing

As the eICU dataset has not been preprocessed during the anonymization, it represents raw data of different measurements using different systems and interfaces. Due to this fact the dataset shows some missing datapoints and artefacts (i.e. by missing or mounting of catheter and probes), as shown in Figure 1. To achieve good model results, the dataset has been preprocessed using different strategies.

4.1 Vital Periodics

As following features have more than 90% missing datapoints and imputing would skew the real dataset, they have been deleted from the dataset: *etco2*, *st1*, *st2*, *st3*, *pasystolic*, *padiastolic*, *pamean*.

Even if the three systemic pressure measurements have more than 50% missing datapoints, they have been kept in the final dataset, because they could have an impact on the ICP prediction. This applies also for the temperature and respiration measurements. Therefore, the missing datapoints within the trend have been filled using forward fill strategy. In cases, where the dataset show missing data points at the beginning of a trend the overall mean has been used, because the forward fill strategy is not applicable here. If a patient does not have any data of a dedicated feature, it has been imputed using the overall mean of the corresponding feature. Some features show artefacts in the dataset due to sensor or handling failures during the measurement, which are not realistic values. The artefacts, have been cleaned by cutting all values outside of the normal range.

Following features have been cleaned from artefacts using the corresponding defined range:

- ICP: 0 – 100
- Systemicdiastolic: 0 – 250
- Systemicsystolic: 0 – 250
- Systemicmean: 0 – 250

The Figure 2 shows an example of pre-processed feature (temperature) using the imputing strategy.

Figure 2: Example of imputing strategy with temperature

4.3 Patient

From the patient table following features have been kept to use for the model development: *patientunitstayid*, *gender*, *age*. The ID features are kept for traceability and merging reasons. First, all missing values have been dropped in the remained dataset. The gender feature contains four different categories, which have been mapped to numeric values to achieve better model performance. The *age* feature contains only one non-numeric value, which represent all patients over 89 years. This value has been transformed into a numeric value, by replacing it with 90.

4.3 Apache Patient Results

From the *apache patient results* table following features have been kept to use for the model development: *apachepatientresultsid*, *patientunitstayid*, *acutephysiologycore* and *apachescore*. The ID features are kept for traceability and merging reasons. This table does not contain any missing values and therefore no further pre-processing is required.

4.4 Final Dataset

After preprocessing of the three different tables, they have been merged into one data frame using the feature *patientunitstayid*. The final dataset contains periodic vital signs and demographic information of 1385 patients and consists of following features: *observationoffset*, *vitalperiodicid*, *patientunitstayid*, *temperature*, *sao2*, *heartrate*, *respiration*, *cvp*, *systemicsystolic*, *systemicdiastolic*, *systemicmean*, *icp*, *gender*, *age*, *apachepatientresultsid*, *acutephysiologycore*, *apachescore*.

The *apachepatientresultsid* and *vitalperiodicid* features are keys created by the relational database and are not relevant for the prediction. Therefore the ID-features have been deleted, before the model training. The *patientunitstayid* has been set as index of the dataset for better traceability. The final dataset consists of following shape: (4400478x14)

3 Results and Discussion

The final dataset has been split into a train, validation and test set to use for the model development using the pareto principle (80/20%). For the model development two iterations have been performed using the XGBoost Regressor (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) and trained with the patient data, because the XGBoost is a very robust tree-based model and offers a feature importance attribute that can be used for model explainability. The mean squared error has been used as the loss function, because it reduces outlier errors in the dataset. For the hyperparameter tuning the hyperopt framework has been used, which is a distributed asynchronous hyperparameter optimization [14]. The goal is to develop a model that will be used as reference to optimize the pre-processing and model-performance for the ICP prediction and develop insights about the feature importance, which could indicate good predictors for ICP.

3.1 Baseline Model (XGBoost Regressor)

In the first iteration a baseline model has been developed with the pre-processed data, to gain better insights on the dataset. Following hyperparameters have been identified resulting a beneficial loss:

- *colsample_bytree*: 0.832
- *gamma*: 9.976
- *max_depth*: 17
- *min_child_weight*: 0.400
- *reg_alpha*: 62
- *reg_lambda*: 0.429

The first iteration shows that using fixed values outside of the dataset range (e.g. -99°C for temperature) to impute missing data are not beneficial for the ICP prediction. The mean squared error (MSE) on the test set of the first model was 1691.833.

Figure 3: Prediction of one patient in first iteration

To evaluate the feature importance from the XGBoost model, the shap values have been used [16,17].

Figure 4: Feature importance of XGBoost (first iteration)

As Figure 4 shows, the XGBoost model detected some features as more important than others, even with a bad MSE. The first model will not be discussed further, because the aim of the first iteration was to gain some insights on the pre-processing of the data and general feasibility of prediction.

3.2 Improved Baseline Model (XGBoost Regressor)

The goal of the second iteration was to improve the performance of the baseline model. Therefore the imputing strategy has been changed to fill the missing values with the forward fill strategy or overall mean (see chapter 4.1). Following hyperparameters have been identified resulting in a good loss:

- colsample_bytree: 0.948
- gamma: 5.037
- max_depth: 36
- min_child_weight: 0.100
- reg_alpha: 300
- reg_lambda: 1.398

The second iteration shows that the data imputation using forward fill strategy and a fixed mean value, improved the model performance with an MSE of 294.995.

Figure 5: Prediction of one patient in second iteration

The Figure 5 shows the prediction of ICP for one patient in the test set. To evaluate the feature importance from the XGBoost model, the shap values have been used.

Figure 6: Feature importance of XGBoost (second iteration)

As the shap value plot shows in Figure 6, the XG Boost model detected the *acutephysiologyscore*, *observationoffset* and *patientunitstayid* as the most important features. This means that model interpreted that there are different patient data and also sequence dependencies for the ICP prediction. As the acute physiology score is the most important feature, this means that the vital signs used for calculation of the acute physiology score and the patient mortality can be used for the prediction of ICP. The acute physiology score is calculated using following vital signs [13]:

- rectal temperature (°C)
- mean arterial pressure (mmHg)
- heart rate (ventricular response)
- respiratory rate (non-ventilated or ventilated)
- oxygenation: A-aDO₂ or PaO₂ (mmHg)
- arterial pH
- serum sodium (mMol/l)
- serum potassium (mMol/l)
- serum creatinine (mg/100 ml)
- hematocrit (%)
- leukocytes (total/mm³)
- Glasgow coma score (GCS)

The ICP correlates with the patient mortality, which has been shown in previous studies. [8,9,10] Following vital signs of the available dataset have been interpreted as important by the XGBoost model:

- systemic mean
- systemic diastolic
- temperature
- heartrate
- cvp

As shown in the listings above, the used dataset contains vital signs, which are also used for the calculation of the acute physiology score (e.g. heart rate, systemic mean, rectal temperature). This confirms that including the vital signs of the acute physiology score, will improve model performance further and can be used for ICP prediction.

4 Limitations

Due to hardware resource limitations the XGBoost models have been trained with a reduced dataset. The data has been reduced to 200000 data points, which corresponds to 65 of 1385 patients. It is expected that the model performance will increase using the whole dataset for model training.

5 Conclusion

The current paper proposes a machine learning approach for patient diagnosis and outcome. As shown within the results, the models are able to predict the ICP using periodic vital signs. Including the periodic vital signs, which are used for the calculation of acute physiology score, could improve the model prediction and give more insights about the correlation of vital signs with the ICP.

6 Outlook

The current study shows a modeling approach using XGBoost models. Future studies can use deep neural networks to further improve the prediction (e.g. bidirectional LSTM or bidirectional GRUs). The potential of using deep neural networks is that they can be fitted with the whole dataset by splitting the dataset batches using a data generator. For instance, each batch can contain data of one single patient. The neural networks are not easy to be explained, as they do not provide a feature importance attribute compared to standard models. To investigate the feature importance of a deep neural network, the feature permutation approach is beneficial. As shown with the results of the XGBoost the acute physiology score is an important feature for ICP prediction. As the score is calculated within the arrival of the patients on the ICU stations, it gives the potential for future studies to include a dataset with a frequent calculation (e.g. daily) of the acute physiology score, in case the continuous measurement of the vital signs is difficult to implement.

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